

AME-M290 confers aminoglycoside resistance in identified multi-drug resistant *P. aeruginosa* and can be treated with Tobramycin and sulfonamide S-03 inhibitor combination

Hassan Amir

In Correspondence with Dr. Christopher Lohans and MICR290 Teaching Team, Department of Biomedical and Molecular Sciences, Queen's University at Kingston

Abstract- The study identified and characterized an unknown bacterial strain (UBS) from a sputum sample (120,000 CFU/ml) of a suspected bacterial pneumonia patient at Kingston General Hospital. Gram staining, biochemical tests, VITEK-2 AST, and 16S rRNA sequencing confirmed identity of *P. aeruginosa* KGH with multi-drug resistance (MDR) to common antibiotics. Plasmid analysis identified an aminoglycoside modifying acetyltransferase encoded by the AME-290 gene utilizing BLASTp. AME-M290 was cloned into pET-28a, expressed by transformed *E. Coli* BL21 (DE3). AME-M290 proteins are purified via size exclusion chromatography and Ni-NTA. Acetyltransferase assay displays AME-M290 acetylation of gentamicin at V_i of 0.1672 $\mu\text{M/s}$. S-02 is more potent with an IC-50 of 19.95 μM , compared to S-03 (IC50 = 80 μM). S-02 is more efficacious where percent inhibition (PI) is 90.43%, relative to S-01 (PI=3.89%). Broth microdilution displayed that tobramycin/S-03 had the lowest MIC (0.06 $\mu\text{g/mL}$) making it the best treatment for MDR *P. aeruginosa* KGH. This study supports dual antibiotic therapies as a viable treatment for AME *P. aeruginosa* resistance.

I. INTRODUCTION

P*seudomonas aeruginosa* is a rod-shaped gram negative bacteria, known to cause nosocomial pneumonia, urinary tract and surgical site infections.(1) *P. aeruginosa* is treated with several antibiotic classes including aminoglycosides. Aminoglycosides like gentamicin impact the ability of bacterial ribosomes in reading mRNA transcripts. This causes alteration of protein structure and function, killing bacteria.

However, *P. aeruginosa* has several resistance mechanisms to antibiotics like aminoglycosides.(2) A hallmark of aminoglycoside resistance is the expression of aminoglycoside-modifying enzymes (AME) made up of three classes including acetyltransferases, phosphotransferases, and nucleotidyltransferases. *P. aeruginosa* strains have demonstrated resistance to gentamicin through the production of acetyltransferases which transfer labeled acetate to gentamicin C complex via acetyl coenzyme A.(3) Phosphotransferases catalyze phosphorylation of the 3'-hydroxyl of kanamycin, decreasing its uptake.(4) Nucleotidyltransferases adenylate the 2"-hydroxyl of tobramycin, altering 30S ribosomal A-site.(5) The acetylated drug can no longer bind to the ribosome, interfering with translation. Other causes of aminoglycoside resistance include overexpression of MexXY-OprM efflux pumps, mutations (*fusA1* and *armZ*) and 16S rRNA molecules.(6)

Aminoglycoside resistance associated with *P. aeruginosa* remains a problem in clinical settings. A study of 200 *P. aeruginosa* clinical isolates found that 48% were resistant to aminoglycosides with 98% of these samples exhibiting MDR.(7) Specifically, 85.4% of the isolates have the gene *aac(6')-Ib* encoding AMEs. A longitudinal study over a 12-year period found variable resistance in *P. aeruginosa* isolates with 4.2% of samples resistant to Gentamicin and Tobramycin, with 2.9% of samples presenting Amikacin resistance.(8) Another study revealed plasmid mediated aminoglycoside resistance in *P. aeruginosa* with 18% of isolates presenting MDR.(9) Due to multi-faceted resistance involving combinations of AMEs and efflux pumps, single antibiotic therapies present limited efficacy with high MICs.(10) Limited efficacy warrants investigation of dual antibiotic-inhibitor therapies.

The objective of the study is to identify and characterize an unknown bacterial strain of a suspected bacterial pneumonia patient for the identification of an effective antibiotic therapy.

II. METHODS

A. SAMPLE COLLECTION AND INITIAL CHARACTERIZATION

A sputum sample is collected from a patient's lungs suspected of bacterial pneumonia presenting a fever, cough, chest pain and shortness of breath. Serial dilutions of the sample are prepared to determine the number of viable bacteria (CFU/ml) in the original sputum sample. 0.5ml of each dilution is placed on to a LB and MacConkey agar plate with overnight incubation at 37 °C. Then, plates colonies are counted following FDA criterion where 25-250 plates are in the recommended range for plate counting. The number of colonies were between 25-250 in the 1/1000 serial dilution for both plates which determined the number of viable bacteria in the original sample.

Gram-stain is performed using standard protocol. Catalase, indole and oxidase tests are carried out for bacterial identity discrimination. The bacterial samples are tested for susceptibility against gentamicin, ciprofloxacin and cefepime through a broth microdilution test. Broader antibiotic susceptibility was conducted utilizing VITEK2 automated antimicrobial susceptibility testing system.

B. SAMPLE SEQUENCING

Unknown bacterial strain colony is transferred to microcentrifuge. 16S rRNA gene is amplified by polymerase chain reaction (PCR) using OneTaq DNA polymerase. Amplified DNA was purified by Spin PCR & DNA Cleanup kit, a spin column-based extraction tool. Purified DNA underwent Sanger Sequencing at the Centre of Applied Genomics at the Hospital for Sick Children. Sequencing output is analyzed by BLASTn.

C. PLASMID ISOLATION AND SEQUENCING

Plasmid DNA is isolated from a grown bacterial isolate structure through the Monarch Spin Miniprep Kit. Then, a NanoDrop microvolume spectrophotometer quantifies DNA concentration. Purified DNA plasmid is submitted to plasmidsaurus for next generation sequencing. Oxford Nanopore technology generates sequencing reads and assembles overlapping reads for the final sequence. Then, BLASTp compares an identified antibiotic resistance putative gene sequence output to known protein sequences.

D. CLONING AND AME-M290 PROTEIN

The AME-M290 gene is amplified into pET-28a plasmid expressed by transformed E. Coli BL21 (DE3) using Q5 High-Fidelity DNA polymerase. The reaction mixture contained 200 µM of dNTPs, 0.5 µM of each of the forward and reverse primers and 100 ng of DNA encoding the AME-M290 gene. Forward and reverse primers are designed with a melting temperature of 65 °C using the NEB T_m calculator. The forward primer will contain BamH1's recognition site and the reverse primer contain NotI's recognition site.

PCR uses the following thermocycling conditions.

98 °C for 30 s

30 cycles of 98 °C for 10 s, 65 °C for 30 s, and 72 °C for 30s.

72 °C for 2 min

Chemically competent E. Coli BL21(DE3) are transformed with pEt-28a-AME M290 plasmid. Transformed cells are grown on an LB agar plate (50 µg/mL kanamycin). Then, E. Coli cells are incubated at 37 °C, 180 rpm, in liquid LB media (50 µg/mL kanamycin). Once OD₆₀₀ = 0.6, 0.1 mM isopropyl β-D-1-

thiogalactopyranoside (IPTG) is added to induce protein production. After IPTG induction, culture is incubated overnight at 18 °C, 180 rpm, then centrifuged at 4,000 rpm and the cell pellet collected. Cells are lysed by sonication and debris removed by centrifugation at 20,000 rpm. The supernatant is loaded onto Ni-NTA resin, washed with Buffer A (50 mM Tris pH 7.5, 100 mM NaCl, 20 mM imidazole), and AME-M290 is eluted with Buffer B (50 mM Tris pH 7.5, 100 mM NaCl, 500 mM imidazole).

AME-M290 proteins are purified using Superdex 200 size exclusion resin, with 50 mM Tris, pH 7.5, 100 mM NaCl buffer. Purified AME-M290 fractions are analyzed by SDS-PAGE (12.5% polyacrylamide, electrophoresis at 180V for 45 minutes). Protein concentration was quantified by UV/Vis spectrophotometry utilizing Beer's Law and BCA assay. Standard curves were generated from serial BSA dilutions (560 nm), and sample concentration calculated from the trendline equation.

E. ANTIBIOTIC-SULFONAMIDE INHIBITOR EVALUATION AND ACETYLTRANSFERASE KINETICS

Acetyltransferase kinetics were measured using 10 nM AME-M290, 50 μ M gentamicin, 100 μ M acetyl-CoA, and 100 μ M 4,4'-dithiopyridine, monitoring pyridine-4-thiolate formation at a wavelength of 324nm every 30 seconds. Molar extinction coefficient was derived from the ProtParam tool. Inhibitors (S-01, S-02, S-03) were tested at 200 μ M. Percent inhibition and IC₅₀ values were calculated from initial velocities. Broth microdilution test in 96-well plates was used to determine MICs for gentamicin, plazomicin, and tobramycin in the presence of or without sulfonamide inhibitors against *P. aeruginosa* KGH.

III. RESULTS

1/1000 serial dilution observed 56 and 60 colonies in LB and MacConkey Agar, respectively. 120,000 CFU/ml and 112,000 CFU/ml of viable bacteria was determined in the original sample in LB and MacConkey agar, respectively. Table 1 and figure 1 summarize serial dilution plate counting results and the formula used for viable bacteria calculation in the sputum sample.

Table 1: Counted colonies in four serial dilutions and original sample after plating on a non-selective LB agar and a selective MacConkey Agar.

Dilution	LB agar	MacConkey Agar
1	confluent	confluent
1/10	confluent	confluent
1/100	475	440
1/1000	56	60
1/10000	3	2

$$\left(\frac{\text{Colonies Counted}}{\text{Volume of Culture Plated}} \right) \times \text{Total Dilution Factor} = \text{Viable Sputum Bacteria}$$

Figure 1: Formula utilized to determine viable bacteria in original sample where volume is measured in ml and total dilution factor refers to cumulative sums of ten-fold dilutions.

Gram stain and biochemical testing aim to understand bacterial morphology and characteristics to discriminate for bacterial identity. Gram staining results observe gram-negative bacilli. Biochemical test results are summarized in table 2.

Table 2: Sputum sample displays catalase-positive, oxidase-positive and indole-negative test results identified through empirical observation.

Biochemical Test	Result
Catalase Test	Bubble formation (positive)
Oxidase Test	Blue (positive)
Indole Test	Yellow (negative)

Initial resistance testing revealed resistance to gentamicin, ciprofloxacin and cefepime. Sample is resistant to common antibiotics, determined using VITEK 2 AST. Blastn analysis of sequencing results revealed multiple top hits associated with *P. aeruginosa* defined by low expect values and high % identity values, some of which are summarized in table 3. The strain of the sputum sample cannot be decided, despite clear identification of genus and species name.

Table 3: PMB16887, AKRC18 and Wesam-2 strains were all top hits with 16S rRNA sequence output according to Blastn.

<i>Pseudomonas Aeruginosa</i> Strain	E value	% Identities
<i>P. aeruginosa</i> PMB16887	3 x 10 ⁻¹⁵¹	100
<i>P. aeruginosa</i> AKRC18	3 x 10 ⁻¹⁵¹	100
<i>P. aeruginosa</i> Wesam-2	3 x 10 ⁻¹⁵¹	100

BLASTp was used to determine similarity of unknown putative antibiotic resistance gene's amino acid sequence to amino acid sequences of known proteins. BLASTp top hit identified the protein as bifunctional aminoglycoside N-acetyltransferase AAC (3)-Ib / aminoglycoside N-acetyltransferase AAC (6')-Ib" [*P. Aeruginosa*] and was defined AME-M290. Table 4 summarizes Blastp alignment values.

Table 4: Top Blastp hit is defined by a high percent identity and positives values, with a low gaps value.

Value Type	Positives	Identity	Gaps
Results	332/334 (99%)	331/334 (99.1%)	0/334 (0%)

AME-M290 recombinant protein was amplified, purified and isolated through PCR, ligation, transformation, Ni-NTA and size exclusion chromatography, followed by SDS-PAGE analysis of protein fractions, shown in figure 1.

Figure 2: SDS-PAGE of eluted protein fractions compared to a molecular weight ladder where fractions 5 and 6 match 37 kDa weight and are likely pure given single bands presence

SDS-PAGE reveals fractions 5 and 6 are likely AME-M290 because band staining aligns with 37 kDa molecular weight. Fractions 5 and 6 are also pure with only one band, suggesting presence of AME-M290. Pure AME-M290 (Fraction 5/6) has an absorbance of 0.089 at 280nm with a molar extinction coefficient of $58330 \text{ M}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$. Purified AME-M290 has a concentration of $1.5258 \times 10^{-6} \text{ M}$, determined using Beer's Law. A is absorbance, I is path length and ϵ is the molar extinction coefficient.

$$c = (A) / (I \times \epsilon)$$

$$c = (0.089) / (1\text{cm} \times 58,330 \text{ M}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1})$$

$$c = 1.5258 \times 10^{-6} \text{ M}$$

Figure 3: Calculating concentration from known absorbance, path length and extinction coefficient

Bovine serum albumin (BSA) standard dilutions are tested for a triplicate of absorbance values at 560nm for a BCA assay producing a calibration curve (Figure 4).

Figure 4: Calibration curve plotting mean triplicate with SD at 560nm for trend line equation of $y=0.0351x + 0.0086$ along a r^2 value of 0.9982.

Absorbance values for AME-M290 are measured using BSA standard outputting an absorbance triplicate of 0.530, 0.482 and 0.508 at 560 nm. Triplicate absorbance mean is 0.507 and was used to calculate concentration of purified AME-M290 which is 14.19 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ using the trendline equation.

$$0.507 = 0.0351 \text{ } 1/(\mu\text{g/mL}) \text{ } x + 0.0086$$

$$(0.507 - 0.0086)/(0.0351/(\mu\text{g/mL})) = x$$

$$x = 14.19 \mu\text{g/mL}$$

Figure 5: Calculation for the concentration of purified AME-M290 using the trendline equation where Y is Mean Absorbance and x is BSA AME-M290 concentration

Monitoring of the acetyltransferase AME-M290 was done through triplicate absorbance value measurements from an acetylation reaction with 50 μM gentamicin, 10 nM AME-M290, 100 μM acetyl-CoA, and 100 μM 4,4'-dithio pyridine were recorded every 30 seconds from 0 to 10 minutes. Triplicates were averaged and Beer's law determined pyridine-4-thiolate concentration at every interval. Assay results are graphed below.

Figure 6: Concentration of pyridine-4-thiolate as a function of time induced by acetyltransferase without sulfonamide inhibitors

Suitable linear range is 0 to 180 seconds, and initial velocity (V_i) without inhibitors is 0.1672 $\mu\text{M/s}$. The reaction was repeated with 200 μM of inhibitors (with S-01, S-02, and S-03. S-01) in same conditions S-02, and S-03. S-01 showed only 3.98% inhibition ($V_i = 0.1607 \mu\text{M/s}$), S-02 showed 90.43% inhibition ($V_i = 0.016 \mu\text{M/s}$) with an IC_{50} of 19.95 μM , and S-03 had an IC_{50} of 80 μM . Initial velocity was determined by plotting concentration values against time and identifying linear range

A 96-well microplate broth microdilution assay was used to determine the MIC values of aminoglycoside antibiotics alone and with acetyltransferase inhibitors against *P. aeruginosa* KGH. Gentamicin displayed no measurable MIC, but gentamicin + S-01 had an MIC of 16 $\mu\text{g/ml}$. Plazomicin had an MIC of 4 $\mu\text{g/mL}$, which decreased to 1 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ with S-01. Tobramycin had MIC of 1 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ and decreased with S-01 (0.25 $\mu\text{g/mL}$) and S-02 (0.13 $\mu\text{g/mL}$). The most effective treatment was tobramycin + S-03 with the lowest MIC of 0.06 $\mu\text{g/ml}$, indicating potent inhibition of *P. aeruginosa* KGH. Figures 7 and 8 show all combinations in the 96 well microplate.

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
A	0.43	0.48	0.42	0.42	0.48	0.38	0.50	0.45	0.46	0.45	0.51	0.00
B	0.00	0.00	0.45	0.51	0.47	0.45	0.43	0.45	0.45	0.49	0.50	0.00
C	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.45	0.43	0.41	0.45	0.44	0.48	0.50	0.00
D	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.43	0.41	0.44	0.48	0.42	0.00
E	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.42	0.41	0.44	0.47	0.46	0.00
F	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.39	0.38	0.42	0.00
G	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.40	0.41	0.00
H	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.44	0.00

Figure 7: Reported MIC values for each antibiotic, inhibitor and combination therapy in 96-well microplate

Row A: gentamicin	Column 1: 32 $\mu\text{g/mL}$
Row B: gentamicin + S-01	Column 2: 16 $\mu\text{g/mL}$
Row C: plazomicin	Column 3: 8 $\mu\text{g/mL}$
Row D: plazomicin + S-01	Column 4: 4 $\mu\text{g/mL}$
Row E: tobramycin	Column 5: 2 $\mu\text{g/mL}$
Row F: tobramycin + S-01	Column 6: 1 $\mu\text{g/mL}$
Row G: tobramycin + S-02	Column 7: 0.5 $\mu\text{g/mL}$
Row H: tobramycin + S-03	Column 8: 0.25 $\mu\text{g/mL}$
	Column 9: 0.13 $\mu\text{g/mL}$
	Column 10: 0.06 $\mu\text{g/mL}$
	Column 11: 0.03 $\mu\text{g/mL}$

Figure 8: Legend For Figure 7 explaining aminoglycosides, inhibitors and combinations alongside concentrations in each column

IV. DISCUSSION

Although a specific strain was not identified, the study identified the UBS as *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* KGH presenting MDR, aligning with studies that *P. aeruginosa* strains present resistance to multiple antibiotics (11). Gram-negative morphology and biochemical results are consistent with *P. aeruginosa*'s reported characteristics such as a lack of tryptophan degradation, presence of catalase enzyme and presence of cytochrome C oxidases (1). Resistance to gentamicin, ciprofloxacin and cefepime is consistent with increasing aminoglycoside resistance in clinical settings (8). Identification and characterization of AME-M290 via Blastp is demonstrated in multiple studies suggesting AMEs as dominant resistant factors in *P. aeruginosa*, specifically acetyltransferases which acetylate aminoglycosides, preventing ribosomal binding (12). Blastp identified the protein as bifunctional aminoglycoside N-acetyltransferase AAC (3)-Ib/AAC (6')-Ib", which is a commonly reported AME family related to aminoglycoside resistance in clinical *P. aeruginosa* isolates (13).

Past literature has shown that acetyltransferases rapidly reduce aminoglycoside activity, leading to low efficacy treatments especially when single aminoglycosides are employed (14). For example, higher initial velocity of gentamicin acetylation is noticed without the presence of inhibitors ($V_i = 0.1672$), relative to inhibitor presence ($V_i = 0.1607 \mu\text{M/s}$ and $V_i = 0.016 \mu\text{M/s}$), in combination with low MICs (Figure 6). Thus, the study's findings strongly support dual therapy agents for the treatment of resistant *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*.

S-02 is more efficacious (PI = 90.43%) than S-01. S-02 is more potent than S-03. S-02 is more potent with an IC₅₀ of 19.95 μM , compared to S-03 (IC₅₀ = 80 μM). However, the best dual therapy in terms of potency was tobramycin + S-03, with the lowest MIC (0.06 $\mu\text{g/mL}$) of all tested antibiotics. Within our results, we see reductions of MICs from single aminoglycosides to aminoglycoside inhibitor therapies, aligning with current literature. For example, Figure 7 displays that Plazomicin had an MIC of 4 $\mu\text{g/mL}$, which decreased to 1 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ with S-01. Tobramycin had MIC of 1 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ and decreased with S-01 (0.25 $\mu\text{g/mL}$) and S-02 (0.13 $\mu\text{g/mL}$). This suggests that sulfonamide inhibitors accentuate potency of aminoglycoside treatments where lower antibiotic is required to fully inhibit bacterial growth. Increased potency may prevent rapid acetylation of aminoglycosides, improving clinical outcomes.

This emphasizes that single therapy is not sufficient for MDR *P. Aeruginosa* due to resistance mechanisms like AMEs. Rather clinicians should look to employ dual therapeutics as they present greater potency and lower MICs. Dual therapy limits selection of resistant mutants, with multiple studies presenting greater extinction rates when antibiotics are used in combination with adjuvants (15).

Low MICs in dual therapy also overcome nephrotoxicity associated with aminoglycosides, decreasing the likelihood of adverse side effects. Current trends report renal toxicity in 10–20% of patients receiving standard single aminoglycoside therapeutic dosages (16). Dual therapeutics which produce lower MICs will have lower prescribed dosages preventing renal injury in clinical settings.

Strengths of the study include its initial characterization of the sputum sample via sequencing and previous initial tests to conclusively rule out other species and genus. For example, growth on MacConkey agar confirmed presence gram-negative bacteria which was conclusively deemed as *Pseudomonas Aeruginosa* after blastn analysis outputted top hits associated with *P. aeruginosa*. Limitations of the study include lack of sequencing on protein fractions 5/6 to determine the conclusive identity of the AME-M290 protein given both presented similar molecular weights. An additional limitation is that only the isolate 's species/genus was identified, and the strain was not identified. This can be improved by incorporating large scale sequencing strategies such as whole genome sequencing to identify the exact bacterial species strain. Future steps include testing antibiotic-inhibitor combinations like Tobramycin/S-03 in a larger patient cohort to determine generalizability of combination

therapy prior to clinical setting implementation. S-02 inhibitor is worth investigating given it's identified efficacy and potency in comparison to other sulfonamide inhibitors.

V. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the objective of the report was to characterize and identify a UBS responsible for bacterial pneumonia-like symptomatic patient at Kingston General Hospital to identify key treatment options. The identified bacterium is MDR *Pseudomonas Aeruginosa* KGH although strain was not identified. The sputum sample species was gram-negative, catalase-positive, oxidase-positive and indole-negative. VITEK-2 AST and susceptibility tests reveal resistance to all common antibiotics. Single aminoglycosides present limited efficacy in treating MDR bacterium and should not be used. AME-M290 an acetyltransferase enzyme was identified as a cause of resistance against single aminoglycosides like gentamicin. S-02 presents high efficacy and potency relative to other sulfonamide inhibitors. Tobramycin/S-03 are the most effective treatment option and should be used. The study supports the viability of antibiotic-inhibitor combinations in treating MDR strains of *P. aeruginosa* given identified low MICs.

WORD COUNT: 2941 WORDS (WITHIN 10-20% OF WORD COUNT)

REFERENCES

1. Holbrook SYL, Garneau-Tsodikova S. 2018. Evaluation of Aminoglycoside and Carbapenem Resistance in a Collection of Drug-Resistant *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* Clinical Isolates. *Microb Drug Resist* 24:1020–1030.
2. Pang Z, Raudonis R, Glick BR, Lin T-J, Cheng Z. 2019. Antibiotic resistance in *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*: mechanisms and alternative therapeutic strategies. *Biotechnol Adv* 37:177–192.
3. Brzezinska M, Benveniste R, Davies J, Daniels PJJ, Weinstein J. 1972. Gentamicin resistance in strains of *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* mediated by enzymic N-acetylation of the deoxystreptamine moiety. *Biochemistry* 11:761–766.
4. Ramirez MS, Tolmasky ME. 2010. Aminoglycoside Modifying Enzymes. *Drug Resist Updat* 13:151–171.
5. Krause KM, Serio AW, Kane TR, Connolly LE. 2016. Aminoglycosides: An Overview. *Cold Spring Harb Perspect Med* 6:a027029.
6. Atassi G, Medernach R, Scheetz M, Nozick S, Rhodes NJ, Murphy-Belcaster M, Murphy KR, Alisoltani A, Ozer EA, Hauser AR. 2023. Genomics of Aminoglycoside Resistance in *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* Bloodstream Infections at a United States Academic Hospital. *Microbiol Spectr* 11:e0508722.
7. Saeli N, Jafari-Ramedani S, Ramazanzadeh R, Nazari M, Sahebkar A, Khademi F. 2024. Prevalence and mechanisms of aminoglycoside resistance among drug-resistant *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* clinical isolates in Iran. *BMC Infect Dis* 24:680.
8. Thomsen J, Menezes GA, Abdulrazzaq NM, Moubareck CA, Senok A, Everett DB. 2023. Evolving trends among *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*: a 12-year retrospective study from the United Arab Emirates. *Front Public Health* 11:1243973.

9. El-Far SW, Abukhatwah MW. 2023. Prevalence of Aminoglycoside Resistance Genes in Clinical Isolates of *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* from Taif, Saudi Arabia-An Emergence Indicative Study. *Microorganisms* 11:2293.
10. Boushra M, Noha, Hassuna N, Gamal, Gad F, Ibrahim R, Waly N. 2024. Detection of possible aminoglycosides resistance mechanisms in *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* resistant isolates. *Novel Research in Microbiology Journal*.
11. Fernández-Billón M, Llambías-Cabot AE, Jordana-Lluch E, Oliver A, Macià MD. 2023. Mechanisms of antibiotic resistance in *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* biofilms. *Biofilm* 5:100129.
12. Vong K, Auclair K. 2012. Understanding and overcoming aminoglycoside resistance caused by N-6'-acetyltransferase. *Medchemcomm* 3:397–407.
13. Ramirez MS, Tolmasky ME. 2010. Aminoglycoside Modifying Enzymes. *Drug Resist Updat* 13:151–171.
14. Blair JMA, Webber MA, Baylay AJ, Ogbolu DO, Piddock LJV. 2015. Molecular mechanisms of antibiotic resistance. *Nat Rev Microbiol* 13:42–51.
15. The Effects of Antibiotic Combination Treatments on *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* Tolerance Evolution and Coexistence with *Stenotrophomonas maltophilia* | *Microbiology Spectrum*.
<https://journals.asm.org/doi/10.1128/spectrum.01842-22>. Retrieved 4 December 2025.
16. Chou C-L, Chuang N-C, Chiu H-W, Liao C-T, Hsu Y-H, Chang T-H. 2022. Aminoglycosides use has a risk of acute kidney injury in patients without prior chronic kidney disease. *Sci Rep* 12:17212.